

DIGITAL LEADERSHIP, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, LEADERSHIP STYLES, AND PERFORMANCE OF BASIC EDUCATION TEACHERS: A CAUSAL MODEL

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Digital Leadership, Emotional Intelligence, Leadership Styles, and Performance of Basic Education Teachers: A Causal Model

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop a causal-comparative model on the influence of digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership style on the performance of basic education teachers. Descriptive-correlational and causal-comparative research designs were employed to identify the predictors of the performance of the basic education teachers. Questionnaires were used as data collection tools after undergoing rigorous scientific testing to ensure accuracy and consistency. Using Raosoft calculator, a sample of 339 basic education teachers in the division of Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines were determined. There is a highly significant relationship between the teachers' performance and the self-management, social awareness, transactional leadership, servant leadership, digital communication skills and self-awareness, technological competence, and transformational leadership, self-management, social awareness, transactional leadership, and servant leadership have significant influence, indicating the importance of organizational skills, empathy, clear expectations, supportive leadership, digital communication skills, self-awareness, technological competence, and transformational leadership. The study implies that teacher training may prioritize self-management, social skills, and supportive leadership while balancing digital and technical skills with interpersonal abilities to enhance overall performance. The model that best fits teachers' performance is causal model 3, which is anchored on social awareness, transactional leadership style, digital innovation adoption, digital communication skills, servant leadership, and self-management.

Keywords: *basic education teachers, digital literacy and reflective practices, communication skills and self-awareness, technical skills with interpersonal abilities*

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, the role of a teacher extends beyond traditional methods of instruction. Digital leadership has emerged as a crucial aspect of education, presenting opportunities and challenges for teachers. One key challenge is the need for educators to develop digital literacy skills to integrate technology into their teaching practices effectively. This includes using digital tools, platforms, and resources to enhance student engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking.

Emotional intelligence is another vital aspect of effective teaching. Teachers with high emotional intelligence can understand and manage their emotions while empathetically connecting with their students. This skill enables them to create a positive classroom environment, foster meaningful relationships, and support students' social-emotional development.

Leadership style plays a significant role in shaping the learning experience for students. Different leadership styles, such as transformational, servant, or transformational, can impact classroom dynamics and student outcomes. A teacher's leadership style should align with the educational goals and values of the institution while promoting student engagement and motivation.

Thus, the performance of basic education teachers is a critical factor in ensuring quality education. Effective teachers demonstrate subject expertise, pedagogical knowledge, and the ability to adapt their teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. Professional development and support are essential in enhancing teacher performance and promoting continuous improvement.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes providing professional development opportunities, fostering a culture of continuous learning, and incorporating technology into teacher training programs. By nurturing digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and effective leadership styles, we can empower primary education teachers to deliver high-quality education and positively impact student outcomes.

The field of education is getting harder and more complex, particularly in the digital age when administrators and managers of schools must learn how to use digital technology (Hamzah et al., 2021). The field of education is continuously evolving, driven by technological advancements and changing educational paradigms. In this era of digital transformation, the role of teachers has become increasingly complex, requiring them to not only possess subject knowledge and pedagogical skills but also adapt to digital tools and technologies. In this context, understanding the factors that influence the performance of basic education teachers has gained significant attention from researchers and policymakers.

This dissertation explored the relationship between digital leadership, emotional intelligence, leadership style, and the performance of basic education teachers. The focus is on examining how these factors interplay and contribute to the overall effectiveness of teachers in the context of digitalized educational settings. Understanding how emotional intelligence, leadership style, and digital leadership affect primary education teachers' performance might help us understand how these elements affect the overall efficacy of educational institutions. It is in this vein that that study was conceptualized.

According to Zhong (2017), emerging instructional technology significantly impacts both higher education and K-12 classrooms, making technology a necessity for 21st-century learners and educators. As educational institutions increasingly integrate technology, digital leaders are crucial in adopting and implementing digital tools and resources. This study investigated how digital leaders influence the performance of primary education teachers and their ability to integrate technology into teaching practices effectively. Emotional intelligence, crucial for effective teaching, involves recognizing, understanding, and managing emotions in oneself and in others. This dissertation examined the impact on teachers' performance and its potential role in mediating the relationship between digital leadership and teacher effectiveness.

Naylor (1999), as cited by Amanchukwu et al. (2015), stated that effective leadership, driven by the heart, requires being visionary, passionate, creative, flexible, inspiring, innovative, courageous, imaginative, experimental, and a catalyst for change. This study examined how leadership styles, including transformational, transactional, and servant leadership, influence classroom climate and teacher-student interactions. Understanding the leadership digital leaders prefer and their effects on basic education teachers' performance is a crucial aspect of this dissertation.

Creating a structural model that integrates digital leadership, emotional intelligence, leadership style, and teacher performance was the aim of this study. The results improved our understanding of exemplary teaching strategies in a digital environment, which will aid institutions and educational policymakers in developing focused interventions to assist basic education instructors. The purpose of this dissertation was to elucidate the connections between teacher performance, emotional intelligence, leadership style, and digital leadership. The insights gained aid academic leaders, policymakers, and practitioners in fostering an optimal teaching and learning environment, ultimately improving educational outcomes and preparing students for the modern world.

Research Questions

This study developed a causal model on the performance of basic education teachers in relation and influence of digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership styles of the teachers. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of digital leadership in terms of:
 - 1.1. technological competence;
 - 1.2. digital communication skills; and
 - 1.3. digital innovation adoption?
2. What is the level of emotional intelligence in terms of:
 - 2.1. self-awareness;
 - 2.2. self-management; and
 - 2.3. social awareness?
3. What is the level of leadership style in terms of:
 - 3.1. transformational leadership;
 - 3.2. transactional leadership; and
 - 3.3. servant leadership?
4. What is the level of performance of the basic education teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' performance and
 - 5.1. digital leadership,
 - 5.2. emotional intelligence, and
 - 5.3. leadership style?
6. Which of the variables, singly or in combination, significantly best influence basic education teachers' performance?
7. What causal model best fits teachers' performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized descriptive-correlational and causal-comparative research designs to identify causes or consequences between independent and dependent variables. Descriptive correlational research design is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection (Quanta, 2017).

On the other hand, the causal-comparative research design was utilized in developing a causal model of digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership style on the performance of basic education teachers. Causal-comparative research is a method used to identify the cause-effect relationship between dependent and independent variables. This relationship is usually a suggested relationship because an independent variable cannot be controlled completely. Unlike correlation research, this doesn't rely on relationships. In a causal-comparative research design, the researcher compares two groups to find out whether the independent variable affects the outcome or the dependent variable. A causal-comparative research design determines whether one variable has a direct influence on the other and why. It identifies the causes of certain occurrences (or non-occurrences). It makes a study descriptive rather than experimental by scrutinizing the relationships among different variables in which the independent variable has already occurred.

Variables can't be manipulated sometimes, but a link between dependent and independent variables is established and the implications of possible causes are used to conclude (Harappa, 2021).

In a causal-comparative design, cause and effect in retrospect is being established. It determined the consequences or causes of differences already existing among or between groups of people. It is appropriate in the study because it helps to determine which variables, singly or in combination, (digital leadership, emotional intelligence, leadership style) best predict teachers' performance. These research designs were used as a blueprint for how this study was conducted and how the data was analyzed.

The study also employed path analysis. Path analysis is a statistical technique that allows users to investigate the effect patterns within a system of variables. It is one of the several types of linear models that examine the impact of a set of predictor variables on multiple dependent variables (Hamilton, 2017).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were three hundred ninety-nine (339) basic education teachers, specifically, public school elementary teachers in the division of Cagayan de Oro City. These 339 sample participants obtained for the study were determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator to obtain the appropriate sample size for the population, with a margin of error of 5%, and a confidence level of 95%. A response distribution of 50% allowed the researcher to obtain an appropriate sample size for the study and ensured that participants were selected in a fair and unbiased manner.

Then, proportionate stratified random sampling was considered to have a sample size from each stratum and to ensure that the data collected was non-biased and reliable. The distribution of the participants is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of Participants of the Study*

DISTRICT	POPULATION (N)	SAMPLE SIZE (n)
Central District	265	31
East District I & II	681	81
North District I & II	379	45
South & Southwest District	652	77
West District I & II	891	181
Grand Total	2 868	339

Instrument

The research instrument used was a survey questionnaire. Data from the study were collected through Google forms like a survey questionnaire. A total of sixty (60) items were measured with a 5-point Likert Scale which was originated by Likert (1932), with five response options ranging from "Strongly Agree" with a score of 5 to "Strongly Disagree" with a score of 1.

Part I. This determined the level of digital leadership of the basic education teachers in terms of (a) Technological Competence, (b) Digital Communication Skills, and (c) Digital Innovation Adoption. Questions were adopted and modified from the study of Yusof (2019).

Part II. This section determined the emotional intelligence of the basic education teachers in terms of (a) Self-Awareness (b) Self-Management, and (c) Social Awareness. Questions on Self-awareness were adopted from the study of Malimit (2022).

Part III. For Basic Education Teachers' Leadership Styles in terms of (a) Transformational Leadership, (b) Transactional Leadership, and (c) Servant Leadership, the research questions were adopted and modified from the study of Guillena (2022).

Part IV. This section covers the key aspects of teacher performance as outlined in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers which was adopted from the study of Acidal (2022).

Procedure

The investigator asked permission from the Dean, School of Teacher Education, LREB or Liceo Research Ethics Board, Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS), Elementary Schools' Principals, and the participants for permission to administer the research instrument questionnaire and collection of required data. Before the survey questionnaires were distributed, the participants were informed about the objectives and purpose of the study.

The participants were informed of the number of participants and about procedures and the treatment for the results of the study. The investigator explained the benefits to the participants and to the educational community. Most importantly, the participants were assured that confidentially of their responses would be kept in high confidentiality and would not be used against them. The participants were given one week to answer the survey questionnaire. The investigator collected and retrieved the questionnaire after the participants answered it completely.

The teachers were assured that they were not vulnerable to any loss of benefits, or performance rating and maintained their protection.

They can freely choose to decide as part of the survey and as much as possible their participation should not be influenced by the researcher's position in any aspect and should not feel threatened should they decide not to join as it was not taken against them.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

Tests on the reliability of the instruments were determined to ensure the internal consistency of the measure of these instruments. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was utilized on both instruments of digital leadership and leadership style. A high Cronbach's alpha coefficient (> 0.7) is expected for a test of knowledge in a subject area or mastery of a particular skill. However, for assessed preferences, a lower correlation among the items is expected. Accordingly, an alpha of 0.75 or greater is acceptable for instruments that measure knowledge and skills while 0.50 or greater is acceptable for attitude and preference assessments (Aperocho, 2014). A Cronbach's Alpha Test was used to test if the researcher-made questionnaire is reliable before it can be distributed to the actual participants of the study. The instruments used in this study were tested for their reliability and internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha.

The Cronbach's alpha tests to see if multiple-question Likert scale surveys are reliable. The tests inform if the questions designed accurately measure the variable of interest.

Table 2. *Reliability Statistics of Instruments*

Instruments	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
Digital Leadership	24	0.881	Good
Emotional Intelligence	15	0.886	Good
Leadership Style	24	0.918	Excellent
Teacher's Performance	33	0.733	Acceptable

Data Analysis

To facilitate the analysis of the interpretation of data, the following statistical tools were employed:

For problem numbers 1, 2, 3, and 4, descriptive statistics were used such as the mean and standard deviation to describe the variables in the study. The mean (average) was deemed the best measure of central tendency (Sykes et al., 2016; Malakar, 2023).

To understand the variation in responses from the data set, the standard deviation was used to measure how much the responses differed from the mean (Elizabeth, 2012). The standard deviation, which is the square root of the variance (Hargrave, 2021), helped how the responses of the 339 basic education teachers were clustered around the mean or spread out.

For problem number 5, Pearson product-moment correlation was used to establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. (Nickolas, 2021).

For problem number 6, multiple linear regression was used to identify the variables that predict the performance of basic education teachers. Moreover, multiple linear regression was used to predict, determine, and characterize the relationship between various indicators of the independent variables perceived by teachers and the variable of teaching competencies. This method identified the degree and nature of the influence between domains, revealing whether a relationship or influence existed (Devault, 2020).

For problem number 7, path analysis was used to develop the causal model that best fits the performance of basic education teachers. This statistical technique allows researchers to assess direct and indirect relationships among variables, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teacher performance (Kline, 2016). By mapping out these relationships, path analysis helps in identifying key predictors and their interactions, offering a robust framework for improving educational outcomes.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the data analysis and findings of the study in response to the problems stated in Chapter 1. The study investigated the teachers' digital leadership, emotional intelligence, leadership style, and the performance of the basic education teachers.

Problem 1. What is the level of digital leadership in terms of: Technological Competence; Digital Communication Skills; and Digital Innovation Adoption?

Table 3 shows the teachers' level of digital leadership in terms of technological competence. As seen in the table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.09$, $SD=.715$ for item 1 "I am confident in my ability to use technology effectively" and a lowest mean score of $M=3.04$, $SD=1.01$ for item number 5 "I often feel insecure and overwhelmed when using technology". The overall mean score is $M=3.65$, $SD=.86$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of digital leadership in terms of technological competence. This finding supports the claim of Suarez- Rodriguez et.al. (2013) that technological competencies can be understood as the series of knowledge and skills that teachers have, allowing them to adequately master various

technological resources needed for their teaching practice. According to Lazarus et.al, (2019), technologically competent teachers can effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices to enhance student learning. They possess the necessary knowledge and skills to use various hardware, software, and digital tools pedagogically soundly.

Table 3. *Level of Digital Leadership in terms of Technological Competence*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1.1 I am confident in my ability to use technology effectively.	4.09	.715	Agree	High
1.2 I can troubleshoot basic technological issues on my own.	3.51	.989	Agree	High
1.3 I am knowledgeable about the latest technological advancements.	3.59	.820	Agree	High
1.4 I can efficiently use technology to complete tasks.	4.03	.791	Agree	High
1.5 I often feel insecure and overwhelmed when using technology.	3.04	1.01	Neutral	Moderately High
Over-all Mean	3.65	0.86	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Teachers' high level of technological competence, as seen by their confidence in utilizing technology and overall positive self-assessment, leads to more productive and engaging classroom experiences for students. This competency enables teachers to smoothly integrate digital resources into their teaching techniques, improving student learning and better preparing them for a technologically driven environment.

Table 4. *Level of Digital Leadership in terms of Digital Communication Skills*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
2.1 I can convey my thoughts and ideas through digital communication.	3.92	.726	Agree	High
2.2 I feel comfortable communicating with others through digital mediums.	4.01	.749	Agree	High
2.3 I can effectively use digital communication tools such as email and instant messaging.	4.14	.847	Agree	High
2.4 I can maintain a professional tone in my digital communication.	4.02	.757	Agree	High
2.5 Communicating through digital mediums feels awkward and unnatural, hindering effective communication.	3.29	1.16	Neutral	Moderately High
Over-all Mean	3.88	0.84	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 4 shows the teachers' level of digital leadership in terms of digital communication skills. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.14$, $SD=.847$ for item 3 "I can effectively use digital communication tools such as email and instant messaging" and a lowest mean score of $M=3.29$, $SD=1.16$ for item number 5 "Communicating through digital mediums feels awkward and unnatural, hindering effective communication". The overall mean score is $M=3.88$, $SD=.84$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data reveal that the respondents have a high level of digital leadership in terms of digital communication skills. This finding supports the claim of Hamzah et.al., (2021) that technologically competent teachers with strong digital communication skills can effectively use various digital tools and platforms to communicate and collaborate with students. This can lead to improved information sharing, problem-solving, and decision-making.

These findings also support the claim of Alajmi (2021) that teachers with advanced digital communication skills can create engaging and interactive learning experiences for students using digital tools and resources. This can lead to increased student motivation, participation, and better learning outcomes. Teachers' high level of digital communication skills, as reflected in their effective use of tools like email and instant messaging, enhances their ability to engage and collaborate with students in real time. This proficiency not only improves information sharing and problem-solving but also fosters more interactive and motivating learning experiences, ultimately leading to better student outcomes.

Table 5 shows the teachers' level of digital leadership in terms of digital innovation adoption. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.26$, $SD=.729$ for item 1 "I am open to exploring new digital tools and technologies" and the lowest mean score of $M=3.20$, $SD=1.20$ for item number 5 "I feel resistant to exploring new digital tools and technologies". The overall mean score is $M=3.88$, $SD=.85$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data reveal that the respondents have a high level of

digital leadership in terms of digital innovation adoption.

Table 5. *Level of Digital Leadership in terms of Digital Innovation Adoption*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
3.1 I am open to exploring new digital tools and technologies.	4.26	.729	Agree	High
3.2 I feel comfortable experimenting with new digital innovations.	4.07	.771	Agree	High
3.3 I can identify opportunities to apply digital innovations in my work.	3.97	.791	Agree	High
3.4 I can adapt to new digital innovations quickly.	3.88	.772	Agree	High
3.5 I feel resistant to exploring new digital tools and technologies.	3.20	1.20	Neutral	Moderately High
Over-all Mean	3.88	0.85	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

This finding supports the claim of Saeed & Kang (2024) that the impact of basic education teachers with high digital leadership in terms of digital innovation adoption is significant. Teachers with high digital leadership skills are more likely to adopt digital innovations in their teaching practices, which can lead to improved student outcomes and enhanced educational experiences. Adopting and incorporating digital innovations into their teaching practices is more common among educators with high digital leadership abilities. These educators have gained a thorough awareness of and proficiency in using digital tools in the classroom. Learning outcomes and educational experiences can be improved when educators with strong digital leadership abilities adopt new digital tools, applications, or strategies. These educators can give their pupils more dynamic, individualized, and engaging learning environments by integrating cutting-edge digital technologies into their lessons. Teachers' high level of digital innovation adoption, as seen by their willingness to try new digital technologies, considerably improves their teaching practices and student results. By incorporating cutting-edge digital tools into their lessons, educators may create more dynamic, individualized, and engaging learning environments that better prepare students for the future.

Table 6. *Summary of the Mean Scores for the Level of Digital Leadership*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Technological Competence	3.65	0.86	Agree	High
Digital Communication Skills	3.88	0.84	Agree	High
Digital innovation Adoption	3.88	0.85	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	3.80	0.85	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 6 presents the summary of the mean scores for the level of digital leadership. As depicted in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=3.88$, $SD=.84$ for digital communication skills and digital innovation adoption ($M=3.88$, $SD=.85$) followed by a mean score of $M=3.65$, $SD=.86$ for technological competence. The overall mean score is $M=3.80$, $SD=.85$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of digital leadership. Several studies have underscored the increasing levels of digital leadership among teachers and its significant impact on education. For instance, a study by Sheninger (2014) highlights how digital leadership empowers educators to enhance their teaching strategies through the integration of technology, fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

Similarly, Liu et al. (2017) found that teachers who exhibit strong digital leadership skills are better equipped to facilitate digital literacy among students, promoting critical thinking and collaborative learning. Additionally, research by Harris & Jones (2020) demonstrates that digital leadership among teachers contributes to a more dynamic and adaptable educational setting, enabling teachers to respond effectively to the evolving technological demands of modern education. These studies collectively indicate that high levels of digital leadership among teachers not only improve instructional practices but also prepare students with essential digital competencies for the future.

Problem 2. What is the level of emotional intelligence in terms of: Self-Awareness; Self-Management; and Social Awareness?

Table 7 shows the teachers' level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-awareness. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.42$, $SD=.617$ for item 5 "I am aware of my strengths and weaknesses" and a lowest mean score of $M=4.15$, $SD=.688$ for item number 2 "I realize the links between my feelings and what I think, do and say". The overall mean score is $M=4.31$, $SD=.65$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-awareness. This finding supports the claim of Dham (2019) which says that a good and emotional teacher is self-aware and also will show empathy towards children, parents, peers, etc. Nowadays children need somebody who will understand their feelings and emotions, guide them, and not judge them in any way. Teachers' high levels of self-awareness, as evidenced by a thorough understanding of their strengths and flaws, allow them to empathize effectively with students, parents, and peers. This

emotional intelligence creates a supportive and nonjudgmental classroom climate, which is essential for meeting students' emotional needs and improving their overall learning experience.

Table 7. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Self-Awareness*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1.1 I always know which emotions I am feeling and why.	4.24	.684	Agree	High
1.2 I realize the links between my feelings and what I think, do and say.	4.15	.688	Agree	High
1.3 I recognize how my feelings affect my performance.	4.35	.687	Agree	High
1.4 I have a guiding awareness of my values and goals.	4.38	.601	Agree	High
1.5 I am aware of my strengths and weaknesses.	4.42	.617	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.31	0.65	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 8 shows the teachers' level of emotional intelligence in terms of self- management. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.28$, $SD=.628$ for item 1 "I can prioritize my tasks effectively" and the lowest mean score of $M=4.06$, $SD=.651$ for item number 4 "I can cope with stress effectively". The overall mean score is $M=4.18$, $SD=.654$ described as agree and interpreted as high.

Table 8. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Self-Management*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
2.1 I can prioritize my tasks effectively.	4.28	.628	Agree	High
2.2 I can manage my time well.	4.22	.659	Agree	High
2.3 I can set realistic goals for myself.	4.20	.647	Agree	High
2.4 I can cope with stress effectively.	4.06	.651	Agree	High
2.5 I can maintain a healthy work-life balance.	4.14	.687	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.18	0.654	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-management. Recent studies have reinforced the significance of high levels of emotional intelligence in terms of self-management among teachers and its positive impacts. A study by Boyatzis et al. (2015) indicates that teachers with advanced self-management skills can regulate their emotions effectively, leading to reduced stress and greater job satisfaction. This ability to manage emotions not only enhances their well-being but also improves their capacity to handle classroom challenges constructively. Similarly, research by Vesely et al. (2016) demonstrates that teachers with strong self-management capabilities exhibit higher resilience and adaptability, which are crucial for maintaining a productive and supportive classroom environment. These skills help teachers navigate the complexities of educational demands while maintaining a positive demeanor. Furthermore, a study by Yin et al. (2017) highlights that self-managed teachers are better at creating emotionally supportive classroom atmospheres, which foster better student engagement and academic performance. These findings collectively underscore the vital role of self-management in emotional intelligence, enhancing teachers' professional effectiveness and contributing to a more conducive learning environment.

Table 9. *Level of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Social Awareness*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
3.1 I can recognize and appreciate diversity in others.	4.24	.637	Agree	High
3.2 I can understand the perspectives of others.	4.22	.633	Agree	High
3.3 I can empathize with others' emotions.	4.26	.657	Agree	High
3.4 I can build and maintain positive relationships with others.	4.38	.629	Agree	High
3.5 I can work collaboratively with others toward a common goal.	4.44	.624	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.30	0.63	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 9 shows the teachers' level of emotional intelligence in terms of social awareness. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.44$, $SD=.624$ for item 5 "I can work collaboratively with others toward a common goal" and a lowest mean score of $M=4.22$, $SD=.633$ for item number 2 "I can understand the perspectives of others". The overall mean score is $M=4.30$, $SD=.63$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of level of emotional intelligence in terms of social awareness. This finding supports the claim of Jennings et al. (2017) that teachers with strong social awareness skills are more attuned to the emotional and social dynamics of their classrooms. This heightened awareness allows them to create more inclusive and empathetic learning environments, which can improve student engagement and reduce behavioral issues. Additionally, Oberle et al. (2016) demonstrated that teachers who possess high social awareness are better equipped to recognize and address the diverse needs of their students, fostering a supportive and respectful classroom culture. Moreover, a study by Collie et al. (2015) indicates that socially aware teachers can build stronger relationships with students and colleagues, which enhances collaboration and reduces stress within the school community. These studies collectively emphasize that high levels of social awareness in teachers contribute to a more positive and effective educational experience, benefiting both teachers and their students.

Table 10. Summary of the Mean Scores of Level of Teachers' Emotional Intelligence

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Self-Awareness	4.31	0.65	Agree	High
Self-Management	4.18	0.65	Agree	High
Social Awareness	4.30	0.63	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.26	0.64	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 10 shows the summary of the mean scores of the level of emotional intelligence in terms of social awareness. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.31$, $SD=.65$ for self-awareness followed by a mean score of $M=4.30$, $SD=.63$, and the lowest mean score of $M=4.18$, $SD=.65$ for self-management. The overall mean score is $M=4.26$, $SD=.64$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of emotional intelligence. This finding is supported by the study of Yin et al. (2017) that teachers with high EI can build stronger relationships with both students and colleagues, enhancing collaboration and creating a more cohesive school community. A study by Jennings et al. (2017) highlights that teachers with high EI are better equipped to manage their emotions, leading to lower stress levels and reduced burnout. This emotional resilience allows them to maintain a positive and supportive classroom environment, which is essential for student learning and engagement. Teachers' high level of emotional intelligence, particularly in social awareness, enables them to build stronger relationships with students and colleagues, fostering a more collaborative and cohesive school community. This emotional resilience helps teachers manage stress and avoid burnout, creating a positive and supportive classroom environment that enhances student learning and engagement.

Problem 3. What is the level of leadership style in terms of: Transformational Leadership; Transactional Leadership; and Servant Leadership?

Table 11 shows the teachers' level of leadership style in terms of transformational leadership. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.57$, $SD=.562$ for item 1 "I set as a good role model for my students to follow" and a lowest mean score of $M=3.11$, $SD=1.18$ for item number 4 "I feel stifled and restricted in my ability to generate new ideas."

The overall mean score is $M=3.70$, $SD=.96$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of leadership style in terms of transformational leadership.

Table 11. Level of Leadership Style in terms of Transformational Leadership

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I set as a good role model for my students to follow.	4.57	.562	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I provide individualized support and guidance to help my students grow and develop.	4.41	.615	Agree	High
3. I often feel demotivated and unable to achieve my full potential under the leadership provided.	3.09	1.22	Agree	High
4. I feel stifled and restricted in my ability to generate new ideas.	3.11	1.18	Agree	High
5. I perceive leadership as inconsistent or lacking in integrity, negatively influencing my behavior.	3.30	1.25	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	3.70	0.96	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

This result corroborates with other studies. A study by Moolenaar et al. (2014) demonstrated that teachers exhibiting transformational leadership qualities, such as inspiring and motivating colleagues, contribute to a more collaborative and innovative school culture.

This leadership style encourages teachers to adopt new teaching methods and engage more deeply with their professional development. Similarly, research by Toprak & Kaya (2017) found that transformational leaders in educational settings positively influence teachers' job satisfaction and commitment by fostering a supportive and trusting environment. This increased job satisfaction often leads to improved teacher retention and a more stable student- learning environment. Teachers' high level of transformational leadership, exemplified by their ability to serve as role models, inspires students and colleagues, fostering a collaborative and innovative school culture. This leadership style not only enhances teachers' job satisfaction and commitment but also leads to improved teacher retention, providing a stable and supportive learning environment for students.

Table 12. *Level of Leadership Style in terms of Transactional Leadership*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
2.1 I set clear expectations for what is expected of me.	4.17	.637	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.2 I am provided with feedback on my performance.	4.10	.681	Agree	High
2.3 I make decisions based on established rules and procedures.	4.24	.583	Agree	High
2.4 I maintain a predictable work environment.	4.09	.675	Agree	High
2.5 Feedback on my performance is scarce or ineffective, leaving me feeling unsupported and undervalued.	3.25	1.31	Neutral	Moderately High
Over-all Mean	3.97	0.77	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 12 shows the teachers' level of leadership style in terms of transactional leadership. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.57$, $SD=.562$ for item 1 "I set as a good role model for my students to follow" and a lowest mean score of $M=3.11$, $SD=1.18$ for item number 4 "I feel stifled and restricted in my ability to generate new ideas.". The overall mean score is $M=3.70$, $SD=.96$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of leadership style in terms of transactional leadership. This result found support from previous studies such as that by Bogler (2016) who indicated that transactional leadership positively impacts teachers' job satisfaction by providing tangible rewards and recognition for their efforts, which can lead to higher motivation and commitment to their roles. These studies collectively emphasize that while transactional leadership may not foster innovation to the same extent as transformational leadership, it plays a crucial role in creating a structured, efficient, and motivated teaching environment.

Table 13. *Level of Leadership Style in terms of Servant Leadership*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
3.1 I am committed to serving the needs of my students.	4.52	.581	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.2 I am empathetic and understanding of my students' needs and perspectives.	4.47	.606	Agree	High
3.3 I create a supportive work environment that encourages personal growth and development.	4.46	.630	Agree	High
3.4 I am willing to listen to feedback and take action to address concerns.	4.55	.590	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.5 I am committed to building positive relationships with my students.	4.64	.537	Strongly Agree	Very High
Over-all Mean	4.53	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 13 shows the teachers' level of leadership style in terms of servant leadership. As seen in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.64$, $SD=.537$ for item 5 "I am committed to building positive relationships with my students" and a lowest mean score of $M=$, $SD=1.18$ for item number 4 "I feel stifled and restricted in my ability to generate new ideas.". The overall mean score is $M=3.70$, $SD=.96$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of leadership style in terms of servant leadership. This finding supports the claim of De Clerq et al. (2021) that servant leadership positively influences teachers' emotional well-being and reduces burnout by promoting a culture of empathy and care. A similar study by Allen

et al. (2015) also stated that servant leadership fosters a collaborative and nurturing school culture, encouraging teachers to share best practices and support each other's professional development. The result also supported the study of Eva et al. (2019) which stated that servant leadership, which prioritizes the growth and well-being of teachers, leads to higher levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Teachers under servant leadership feel more supported and valued, which enhances their motivation and performance. In real-life educational settings, high levels of servant leadership among teachers contribute to a nurturing and supportive environment where empathy and care are prioritized. This approach not only enhances teachers' emotional well-being and reduces burnout but also fosters a collaborative culture that supports professional growth and improves overall job satisfaction and commitment among educators.

Table 14. Summary of Mean Scores of the Level of Teachers' Leadership Styles

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Transformational Leadership	3.70	0.96	Agree	High
Transactional Leadership	3.97	0.77	Agree	High
Servant Leadership	4.53	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
Over-all Mean	4.07	0.77	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 14 shows the summary of mean scores of the level of teachers' leadership style. As seen in the table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.53$, $SD=.58$ for servant leadership followed by a mean score of $M=3.97$, $SD=.77$, and the lowest mean score of $M=3.70$, $SD=.96$ for transformational leadership. The overall mean score is $M=4.07$, $SD=.77$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of leadership style. This finding affirms the claim of Hallinger & Heck (2014) which revealed that teachers who exhibit high leadership qualities, significantly enhance student learning by creating an engaging and supportive learning environment. This type of leadership fosters a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in teaching practices. According to Liu et al. (2018) transformational leadership among teachers, characterized by inspiration and motivation, leads to higher student engagement and academic achievement. Teachers who adopt transformational leadership are more likely to implement innovative teaching strategies that cater to diverse student needs.

Problem 4. What is the level of performance of the basic education teachers?

Table 15. Level of Performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas	4.57	.578	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I used research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	4.22	.668	Agree	High
3. I ensured the positive use of ICT to facilitate the teaching and learning process.	4.43	.664	Agree	High
4. I used a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills	4.43	.579	Agree	High
5. I applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	4.33	.600	Agree	High
6. I displayed proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.43	.589	Agree	High
7. I used effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement.	4.46	.591	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.41	0.61	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 15 presents the level of performance of teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. As shown in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.57$, $SD=.578$ for item number 1 "I applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas" and the lowest mean score of $M=4.22$, $SD=.68$ for item number 2 "I used research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice". The overall mean score is $M=4.41$, $SD=.61$, described as agree and interpreted

as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. This implies that teachers are proficient in applying content across the curriculum, effectively integrating subject matter into various areas of study. Mastery of the subject matter is an essential skill for teachers, as it directly influences the quality of the teaching and learning process in schools Kamamia et al. (2014).

According to Heggart (2016), teachers must thoroughly understand the subjects they teach, as this ensures they can effectively convey key concepts to learners and correct any misconceptions. This comprehensive grasp of the subject matter is crucial for effective teaching and for fostering a deep understanding among students. In practice, teachers' high levels of content knowledge and pedagogy guarantee that their expertise is effectively translated into meaningful learning experiences for students across multiple courses. This competency not only improves classroom instruction but also creates a learning environment in which students can understand and apply subject matter information with confidence and accuracy.

Table 16. Level of Performance in terms of Diversity of Learners

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I used differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.	4.38	.626	Agree	High
2. I established a learner-centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socioeconomic, and religious backgrounds	4.34	.603	Agree	High
3. I designed, adapted, and implemented teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents	4.26	.692	Agree	High
4. I planned and delivered teaching strategies that were responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances.	4.23	.709	Agree	High
5. I adapted and used culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous groups.	4.14	.774	Agree	High
6. I managed classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments	4.40	.623	Agree	High
7. I managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.41	.609	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.31	0.66	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 16 presents the level of performance of teachers in terms of the diversity of learners. As shown in the table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.41$, $SD=.609$ for item number 7 "I managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments" and the lowest mean score of $M=4.23$, $SD=.709$ for item number 4 "I planned and delivered teaching strategies that are responsive to the special educational needs of learners in difficult circumstances". The overall mean score is $M=4.31$, $D=.66$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of diversity of learners. The study of Santamaria (2014) supports the finding that teachers who excel in recognizing and responding to diverse learner needs can create more inclusive and equitable classrooms. This approach not only supports academic achievement but also fosters a sense of belonging among all students. Gay (2018) emphasized that teachers skilled in differentiating instruction based on student diversity can better meet individual learning needs, thereby improving overall educational outcomes. These findings suggest that teachers who excel in diverse learning environments enhance student engagement, promote equity, and boost academic success, ultimately contributing to more effective and inclusive education.

Table 17 presents the Level of Performance of Teachers in terms of Curriculum and Planning. As shown in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.42$, $SD=.603$ for item number 2 "I set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are

aligned with learning competencies” and the lowest mean score of $M=4.29$, $SD=.635$ for item number 4 “I participated in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice”. The overall mean score is $M=4.36$, $D=.62$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data reveal that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of curriculum and planning. This highlights the importance of teachers in creating learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity. It underscores the significance of teachers' knowledge, understanding, and respect for the diverse characteristics and experiences of learners in planning and designing learning opportunities. This approach promotes the celebration of diversity in the classroom and emphasizes the necessity of differentiated teaching practices to prepare all learners to be successful citizens in an evolving local and global context.

Table 17. *Level of Performance in terms of Curriculum and Planning*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I planned, managed, and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	4.34	.622	Agree	High
2. I set achievable and appropriate learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies.	4.42	.603	Agree	High
3. I adapted and implemented learning programs that ensure relevance and responsiveness to the needs of all learners.	4.38	.621	Agree	High
4. I participated in collegial discussions that used teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice.	4.29	.635	Agree	High
5. I selected, developed, organized, and used appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	4.35	.629	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.36	0.62	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

This finding supports the claim of Possi & Milinga (2017), which stated that data from inclusive classrooms were analyzed with a focus on three aspects of learner diversity: language of instruction, gender, and disability issues. The findings demonstrated the complexity of teaching in classrooms with students who have diverse educational needs and backgrounds, necessitating a high level of teacher attention in the teaching and learning processes. Acdal (2022), stated in her study that, planning the school curriculum in terms of subjects and qualifications is just the initial step. A high-performing school's curriculum offers a learning experience that exceeds the sum of the qualifications, subjects, and activities listed on the schedule. This is achieved through meticulous planning that integrates learning within, across, and between subjects and activities.

Table 18. *Level of Performance in terms of Assessing and Reporting*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I designed, selected, organized, and used diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.42	.602	Agree	High
2. I monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	4.45	.620	Agree	High
3. I used strategies for providing timely, accurate, and constructive feedback to improve learner performance.	4.36	.609	Agree	High
4. I communicated promptly and the learners' needs, progress, and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	4.41	.629	Agree	High
5. I utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs.	4.35	.625	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.40	0.61	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 18 presents the Level of Performance of Teachers in terms of Assessing and Reporting. As shown in the table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.45$, $SD=.620$ for item number 2 “I monitored and evaluated learner progress and a achievement using learner attainment data” and a lowest mean score of $M=4.35$, $SD=.625$ for item number 5 “I utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs”. The overall mean score is $M=4.40$, $SD=.61$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of assessing and reporting.

Assessment and reporting collaborate to help students achieve high standards and provide a foundation for guiding future learning, while also informing parents about their child's progress. Effective teaching fosters student learning in any circumstances and conditions. When combined with strong leadership, adequate resources, and meaningful stakeholder engagement, effective teaching has the potential to transform public education and ensure excellent public schools for every student.

According to the study by Black & William (2018), teachers who excel in assessment practices provide more accurate and constructive feedback, which enhances student learning and motivation. Effective assessment allows teachers to identify learning gaps and tailor instruction to meet individual student needs.

The study find support in Hattie & Timperley (2017), which stated that proficient reporting practices help teachers communicate student progress more effectively to parents and stakeholders, fostering a collaborative approach to student development. In real-world educational settings, instructors' great proficiency in assessing and reporting allows them to correctly track student development and modify their teaching tactics accordingly. This creates a supportive learning environment in which students receive immediate feedback and tailored instruction, while parents and stakeholders are kept informed, encouraging collaborative efforts to support student accomplishment and progress.

Table 19. *Level of Performance in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement*

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1.	I maintained learning environments that were responsive to community contexts.	4.39	.636	Agree	High
2.	I built relationships with parents/guardians and the wider school community to facilitate involvement in the educative process.	4.42	.621	Agree	High
3.	I reviewed regularly personal teaching practices using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.	4.37	.609	Agree	High
4.	I complied with and implemented school policies and procedures consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	4.46	.596	Agree	High
Over-all Mean		4.41	0.61	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 19 presents the level of performance of teachers in terms of community linkages and professional engagement. As shown in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.46$, $SD=.596$ for item number 4 “I complied with and implemented school policies and procedures consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders” and the lowest mean score of $M=4.37$, $SD=.609$ for item number 3 “I reviewed regularly personal teaching practice using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers”. The overall mean score is $M=4.41$, $SD=.61$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of community linkages and professional engagement. This finding supports the claim of Epstein & Sanders (2018) that teachers who actively engage with the community and establish strong linkages can draw on community resources to enrich the educational experience, thereby enhancing student learning and well-being.

Additionally, a study conducted by by Lieberman & Mace (2014), highlighted that teachers who are involved in professional networks and learning communities are better equipped to implement innovative teaching strategies and address diverse student needs. The teachers' excellent performance in community links and professional engagement fosters collaborative partnerships with students, parents, and stakeholders, which improves educational results through shared resources and support. By participating in professional networks and following ethical principles, educators help to create a coherent educational environment that promotes continuous learning and successful teaching approaches adapted to varied student requirements.

Table 20 presents the level of performance of teachers in terms of personal growth and professional development. As shown in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.50$, $SD=.592$ for item number 5 “I set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers” and the lowest mean score of $M=4.36$, $SD=.639$ for item number 4 “I developed a personal professional improvement plan based on reflection of one’s practice and ongoing professional learning”. The overall mean score is $M=4.42$, $SD=.62$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a high level of performance in terms of personal growth and professional development. This finding supports the claim of Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) that teachers who engage in continuous professional development exhibit improved instructional practices, leading to higher student achievement and engagement.

Table 20. *Level of Performance in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I applied a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered.	4.40	.623	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I adopted practices that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as a caring attitude, respect, and integrity	4.47	.611	Agree	High
3. I participated in professional networks to share knowledge and enhance practice.	4.36	.639	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I developed a personal professional improvement plan based on reflection of one’s practice and ongoing professional learning.	4.39	.676	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. I set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.	4.50	.592	Strongly Agree	Very High
Over-all Mean	4.42	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

A similar study was also conducted by Desimone & Garet (2015), which found that targeted professional development programs help teachers deepen their content knowledge and pedagogical skills, which directly enhances their ability to meet diverse student needs. In real- life educational contexts, teachers’ outstanding performance in personal growth and professional development demonstrates their dedication to improving teaching practices and staying current with educational standards. This dedication not only improves teaching effectiveness and student engagement but also promotes a culture of lifelong learning that benefits both educators and students.

Table 21. *Summary of the Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of DepEd Basic Education Teachers*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.41	0.61	Agree	High
Diversity of Learners	4.31	0.66	Agree	High
Curriculum and Planning.	4.36	0.62	Agree	High
Assessing and Reporting	4.40	0.61	Agree	High
Professional Engagement.	4.41	0.61	Agree	High
Personal Growth and Professional Development	4.42	0.62	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	4.39	0.62	Agree	High

Legend: 4.51-5.00, Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.51-4.50, Agree, High; 2.51-3.50, Neutral, Moderately High; 1.51-2.50, Disagree, Low; 1.00-1.50, Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 21 presents the summary of the mean scores of the level of performance of teachers using the PPST. As shown in the Table, respondents obtained the highest mean score of $M=4.42$, $SD=.62$ for personal growth and professional development, followed by a mean score of $M=4.41$, $SD=.61$ for content knowledge and pedagogy, a mean score again of $M=4.41$, $SD=.53$ for content knowledge and pedagogy, a mean score again of $M=4.41$, $SD=.61$ for professional engagement, a mean score of $M=4.40$, $SD=.61$ for assessing and reporting, a mean score of $M=4.36$, $SD=.62$ for curriculum and planning, and a lowest mean score of $M=4.31$, $SD=.66$ for diversity of learners.

The overall mean score is $M=4.39$, $D=.62$ described as agree and interpreted as high. The data revealed that the respondents have a very satisfactory assessment of the level of their performance. This finding supports the claim of Taylor and Tayler (2014) that teachers who receive high ratings in performance assessments tend to exhibit greater job satisfaction and motivation, which translates into improved teaching quality and student outcomes.

Research by Rockoff et al. (2014), revealed a correlation between positive performance evaluations and increased teacher retention, indicating that when teachers feel recognized and valued, they are more likely to remain in the profession and contribute to their schools. Similarly, Kraft & Papay (2014) emphasized that teachers who receive constructive feedback and high-performance ratings are more inclined to engage in professional development activities, thereby enhancing their instructional skills and effectiveness. These findings collectively suggest that very satisfactory performance assessments not only boost teachers' confidence and professional growth but also lead to better educational experiences and achievements for their students.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' performance and digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership style?

Table 22 shows the results of the correlation analysis between the teachers' performance and: digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership style. As depicted in the Table, Servant Leadership ($r = .675, p < .05$); and Emotional Intelligence ($r = 0.614, p < .05$); Self-management ($r = .559, p < .05$); Leadership Styles ($r = .556, p < .05$); Social Awareness ($r = .493, p < .05$); Digital Innovation Adoption ($r = .403, p < .05$); Digital Communication Skills ($r = .402, p < .05$); Technological Competence ($r = .267, p < .05$); and Transformational Leadership ($r = .200, p < .05$). The results indicate that all examined factors such as digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and various leadership styles are significantly correlated with teachers' performance. The highest correlations are observed with Servant Leadership and Emotional Intelligence, suggesting these are particularly influential. These findings imply that enhancing these specific aspects could lead to improved teacher performance.

Table 22. *Relationship between the Teachers' Performance, Digital Leadership, Emotional Intelligence, and Leadership Style*

Variables	N	r	p-value	Interpretation
Technological Competence	339	.267	.000	Significant
Digital Communication Skills	339	.402	.000	Significant
Digital innovation Adoption	339	.403	.000	Significant
Digital Leadership	339	.400	.000	Significant
Self-Awareness	339	.493	.000	Significant
Self-Management	339	.559	.000	Significant
Social Awareness	339	.566	.000	Significant
Emotional Intelligence	339	.614	.000	Significant
Transformational Leadership	339	.200	.000	Significant
Transactional Leadership	339	.556	.000	Significant
Servant Leadership	339	.675	.000	Significant
Leadership Styles	339	.556	.000	Significant

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Awareness ($r = .493, p < .05$); Digital Innovation Adoption ($r = .403, p < .05$); Digital Communication Skills ($r = .402, p < .05$); Technological Competence ($r = .267, p < .05$); and Transformational Leadership ($r = .200, p < .05$). The results indicate that all examined factors such as digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and various leadership styles are significantly correlated with teachers' performance. The highest correlations are observed with Servant Leadership and Emotional Intelligence, suggesting these are particularly influential. These findings imply that enhancing these specific aspects could lead to improved teacher performance.

Self-management ($p < .05$), Social Awareness ($p < .05$), Transactional Leadership ($p < .05$), Servant Leadership ($p < .05$), and Leadership Styles ($p < .05$) have a large/strong positive significant relationship on Teachers' Performance. In addition, Digital Communication Skills ($p < .05$), and Self-Awareness ($p < .05$) have a moderate positive significant relationship on teachers' performance. Furthermore, Technological Competence ($p < .05$) and Transformational Leadership ($p < .05$) have a weak/small significant relationship with teachers' performance.

As shown in the Table, emotional intelligence, leadership styles, digital competencies, self-management, social awareness, emotional intelligence, transactional leadership, servant leadership, and leadership styles all have significant relationships with teachers' performance. This implies that the higher the levels of emotional intelligence, leadership styles, digital competencies, self-management, social awareness, emotional intelligence, transactional leadership, servant leadership, and leadership styles of basic education teachers, the higher their performance.

These findings confirm Goleman's (2014) argument that high emotional intelligence improves job performance by creating a supportive and collaborative work environment. Furthermore, good digital communication skills and self-awareness were moderately connected to improved teacher performance, emphasizing the importance of educators being able to traverse digital platforms, a notion echoed by Shenger (2019) in his study of digital leadership in education.

Problem 6. Which of the variables, singly or in combination, significantly best influence basic education teachers' performance?

Table 23 presents the results of multiple regression analysis for the variables that singly or in combination influence teachers' performance. As depicted in the table, the R-value was .747 signifying a large/strong positive relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. The R² value of 0.557 implies that the predictor variables used in this study explained 55.7 % of the variability of teachers' performance. The probability value of $p=0.000$ ($F=9, 329$) indicates that the model on teachers' performance and the predictor variables are significant. Of the nine variables, the best predictor is servant leadership ($p<.05$, $Beta=.440$) followed by transactional leadership ($p<.05$, $Beta=.211$), and self-management ($p<.05$, $Beta=.179$).

Table 23. Multiple Regression Analysis of the Variables that Singly or in Combination Influence Basic Education Teachers' Performance

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t			
(Constant)	.806	.192		4.198	.000	Significant	
Technological Competence	-.007	.044	-.009	-.154	.877	Not Significant	
Digital Communication Skills	.058	.050	.074	1.164	.245	Not Significant	
Digital innovation Adoption	.075	.044	.098	1.689	.092	Not Significant	
Self-Awareness	.000	.047	-.001	-.010	.992	Not Significant	
Self-Management	.151	.046	.179	3.282	.001	Significant	
Social Awareness	.068	.051	.080	1.318	.188	Not Significant	
Transactional Leadership	.216	.073	.211	2.953	.003	Significant	
Servant Leadership	.407	.055	.440	7.437	.000	Significant	
Leadership Styles	-.132	.086	-.125	-1.539	.125	Not Significant	
Significant							
R=.747 R ² =.557 F(9/329)=46.03 P-value=.000							

Meanwhile, the other variables namely technological competence ($p>.05$), digital communication skills ($p>.05$), digital innovation adoption ($p>.05$), self-awareness ($p>.05$), social awareness ($p>.05$), and leadership styles ($p>.05$) statistically failed to predict teachers' performance since their probability values were higher than the alpha value of .05.

The regression equation model of this study is $Y'=.806 + .407X_1 + .216X_2 + .151X_3$ Where:

Y' =Teachers' Performance

.112= is the constant X_1 = Servant Leadership

X_2 = Transactional Leadership X_3 = Self-Management

The regression equation implies that the teachers' performance was significantly influenced/predicted by three variables namely servant leadership, transactional leadership, and self-management. As to the extent of the direct effect of the said variables on teachers' performance, for every one-point increase in servant leadership, the teachers' performance will have an increase of .407. Meanwhile, with a point increase of transactional leadership, the teachers' performance will have increase of .216, and with a one-point increase of self-management, the teachers' performance will have an increase of .151.

The results of the multiple regression analysis suggest that certain variables, specifically, self-management, transactional leadership, and servant leadership, significantly predict and influence teachers' performance, underscoring their importance in enhancing teaching effectiveness and overall educational outcomes. Several related studies confirm these findings by demonstrating the impact of these variables on teachers' performance. A study by Wong et al. (2014) showed that self-management skills, such as time and stress management, positively correlate with teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. A similar study was also conducted by Bass & Avolio (2014) emphasized the significance of transactional and servant leadership styles in creating a supportive and structured school environment, leading to enhanced teacher morale and performance. In addition to this, Leithwood et al. (2016), found that servant leadership, characterized by prioritizing others' needs and collective goals, is associated with increased teacher commitment and job satisfaction, resulting in improved teaching performance. These studies generally indicate that self-management skills, transactional leadership, and servant leadership are critical in improving teachers' performance and fostering a positive school climate, benefiting

both educators and students. The findings of this study emphasize the importance of self-management, transactional leadership, and servant leadership in predicting teacher effectiveness and improving educational outcomes. These findings imply that cultivating these characteristics among educators can help to create a more supportive school atmosphere and improve teaching effectiveness, ultimately benefiting both instructors and students in real-world educational settings.

Problem 7. What causal model best fits teachers’ performance?

Table 24. *Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 1 of Basic Education Teachers’ Performance*

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
Technological Competence	-.010	.000	-.010
Digital Communication Skills	.085	.000	.085
Digital Innovation Adoption	.113	.000	.113
Self-Awareness	-.001	.000	-.001
Self-Management	.207	.000	.207
Social Awareness	.093	.000	.093
Leadership Styles	-.145	.000	-.145
Transactional Leadership	.224	.000	.224
Servant Leadership	.508	.000	.508

TC- Technological Competence *SOCA-Social Awareness*
DCS- Digital Communication Skills *LEADST-Leadership Styles*
DI- Digital innovation Adoption *TRLS-Transactional Leadership*
SA-Self-Awareness *SL-Servant Leadership*
SM-Self-Management *PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers*

Table 24 shows the direct, indirect, and total effects of causal model 1 on basic education teachers’ performance. As depicted in the Table, of the nine independent or exogenous variables used to model the teachers’ performance, SL obtained the highest total effect ($\beta = .508$) followed by TRLS ($\beta = .224$), SM ($\beta = .207$), LEADST ($\beta = -.145$), DI ($\beta = .113$),

SOCA ($\beta = .093$), DCS ($\beta = .085$), TC ($\beta = -.010$), and SA ($\beta = -.001$). The result implies that certain variables, particularly servant leadership, transactional leadership, self-management, and leadership styles, significantly influence basic education teachers’ performance. These findings highlight the importance of these factors in shaping teaching effectiveness and overall educational outcomes. Several related studies support these findings by demonstrating the impact of these variables on teachers’ performance.

A study conducted by Leithwood et al. (2016) revealed that servant leadership, characterized by prioritizing the needs of others and collective goals, is linked to increased teacher commitment and job satisfaction, ultimately resulting in improved teaching performance. Also, Bass & Avolio (2014) emphasized the importance of transactional and servant leadership styles in fostering a supportive and structured school environment, leading to enhanced teacher morale and performance. Findings from Wong et al. (2014), demonstrated that self-management skills, such as effective time and stress management, positively correlate with teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. These studies indicate that servant leadership, transactional leadership, self-management, and leadership styles significantly influence teachers’ performance, highlighting the necessity of addressing these factors in teacher development and support initiatives.

Table 25. *Regression Weights of Causal Model 1 of Basic Education Teachers’ Performance*

Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	P
PPST <--- TC	-.007	.028	-2.36	-.010	.813
PPST <--- DCS	.058	.028	2.044	.085	.041
PPST <--- DI	.075	.028	2.707	.113	.007
PPST <--- SA	.000	.032	-.015	-.001	.988
PPST <--- SM	.151	.031	4.944	.207	***
PPST <--- SOCA	.068	.030	2.222	.093	.026
PPST <--- LEADST	-.132	.038	-3.460	-.145	***
PPST <--- TRLS	.216	.037	5.832	.244	***
PPST <--- SL	.407	.033	12.172	.508	***

*Decision: P < .05 (***) is Significant and P > .05 Not Significant*
TC- Technological Competence *SOCA-Social Awareness*
DCS- Digital Communication Skills *LEADST-Leadership Styles*
DI- Digital innovation Adoption *TRLS-Transactional Leadership*
SA-Self-Awareness *SL-Servant Leadership*
SM-Self-Management *PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers*

Table 25 shows the regression weights of Causal Model 1 of teachers’ performance. As seen in the table, the variables DCS ($p < .05$), DI ($p < .05$), SM ($p < .05$), SOCA ($p < .05$), LEADST ($p < .05$), TRLS ($p < .05$), and SL ($p < .05$) have significantly influenced/predicted teachers’ performance while the TC ($p > .05$), and SA ($p > .05$), statistically failed to influence/predict the teachers’ performance. This suggests that these variables play a meaningful role in shaping teachers’ performance outcomes. On the other hand, the variables technological competence (TC) and self-awareness (SA) did not show significant influence or prediction on teachers’ performance, as

their p-values were greater than .05. This implies that these particular factors may not have a substantial impact on teachers' overall performance, at least within the context of the analyzed model.

Table 26. *Standard Fit Indices in Causal Model 1 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance*

Standard Indices	Standard Value Per Criterion	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	<2	54.87
P-Value	>.05	.000
NFI	>.95	.122
TLI	>.95	-.099
CFI	>.95	.121
GFI	>.95	.373
RMSEA	<.05	.399

Legend

CMIN/DF- Chi-Square Minimum/ Degrees of Freedom

CFI - Comparative Fit Index

RMSEA - Root Mean Square Error of Approximation

NFI - Normed Fit Index

TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index

GFI - Goodness of Fit Index

Table 26 presents the standard of fit indices in Causal Model 1 of Teachers' Performance. As shown in the table, the model fit value of CMIN/DF is 54.87 which is greater than 2, p-value is .000 which is less than .05, Normed Fit Index-NFI is .122 which is less than .95, Tucker-Lewis Index-TLI is -.099 which is less than .95, Comparative Fit Index-CFI is .121 which is less than .95, Goodness of Fit Index-GFI is .373 which is less than .95, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation-RMSEA is .399 which is greater than .05. The data revealed that the causal model 1 fit value of the seven standard indices failed to comply with the standard value of the seven indices thus it can be regarded as not the best fit causal model of Teachers' Performance.

Table 27. *Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 2 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance*

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
Digital Communication Skills	.085	.000	.073
Digital innovation AdoptionI	.113	.000	.097
Self- Management	.207	.000	.184
Social Awareness	.093	.000	.080
Leadership Style	-.145	.000	-.124
Transactional Leadership	.224	.000	.213
Servant Leadership	.508	.000	.459

TC- Technological Competence

DCS- Digital Communication Skills

DI- Digital innovation Adoption

SA-Self-Awareness

SM-Self-Management

SOCA-Social Awareness

LEADST-Leadership Styles

TRLS-Transactional Leadership

SL-Servant Leadership

PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers

Table 27 shows the direct, indirect, and total effects of causal model 2 on basic education teachers' performance. As depicted in the table, of the seven independent or exogenous variables used to model the teachers' performance, Servant Leadership obtained the highest total effect ($\beta=.449$) followed by Transactional Leadership ($\beta=.213$), Self- Management ($\beta=.184$), Leadership Styles ($\beta=-.124$), Digital Innovation ($\beta=.097$), Social Awareness ($\beta=.080$), and Digital Communication Skills ($\beta=.073$).

These results have several implications for teachers and educational stakeholders. Firstly, they highlight the importance of leadership styles, particularly servant and transactional leadership, in shaping teachers' performance outcomes. Servant leadership, characterized by prioritizing others' needs and collective goals, has been associated with increased teacher commitment and job satisfaction, ultimately leading to improved teaching performance Leithwood et al., (2016). Similarly, Bass & Avolio (2014) emphasized the significance of transactional leadership in creating a supportive and structured school environment, leading to enhanced teacher morale and performance.

Table 28 shows the regression weights of Causal Model 2 of teachers' performance. As seen in the table, the variables TRLS ($p<.05$), SL ($p<.05$), and SM($p<.05$) have significantly influenced/predicted teachers' performance while the LEADST ($p>.05$), DCS($p>.05$), DI ($p>.05$) and SOCA ($p>.05$), statistically failed to influence/predict the teachers' performance.

The findings of Causal Model 2, which show that transactional leadership (TRLS), servant leadership (SL), and self-management (SM) significantly influence teachers' performance, are well-supported by recent literature. Firstly, the positive impact of transactional leadership on teacher performance is highlighted in a study by Podsakoff et al. (2018), which found that transactional leadership behaviors, such as contingent rewards and management by exception, significantly enhance organizational effectiveness and employee performance, including that of teachers.

Servant leadership (SL) has also been recognized for its significant influence on teachers' performance. Eva et al. (2019) conducted a

comprehensive meta-analysis and found that servant leadership, characterized by its focus on serving and empowering employees, fosters a supportive work environment that enhances job satisfaction and performance among teachers. This leadership style promotes a culture of trust and collaboration, which is crucial for effective teaching and professional growth.

Table 28. *Regression Weights of Causal Model 2 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance*

	Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	P
PPST	<--- LEADST	-.132	.085	-1.557	-.124	.120
PPST	<--- TRLS	.217	.072	3.020	.213	.003
PPST	<--- SL	.407	.052	7.872	.459	***
PPST	<--- DCS	.055	.042	1.292	.073	.196
PPST	<--- DI	.072	.041	1.763	.097	.078
PPST	<--- SM	.151	.045	3.368	.184	***
PPST	<--- SOCA	.067	.047	1.434	.080	.152

Decision: $P < .05$ (***) is Significant and $P > .05$ Not Significant

TC- Technological Competence

DCS- Digital Communication Skills

DI- Digital innovation Adoption

SA-Self-Awareness

SM-Self-Management

SOCA-Social Awareness

LEADST-Leadership Styles

TRLS-Transactional Leadership

SL-Servant Leadership

PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers

In addition to this, self-management (SM) has been identified as a key predictor of teacher performance. According to a study by Boyatzis & McKee (2014), self-management skills, including emotional regulation, time management, and personal goal setting, are critical for teachers to maintain high-performance levels. Teachers who excel in self-management are better equipped to handle classroom challenges and workload, leading to improved teaching outcomes.

The variables such as leadership styles (LEADST), digital communication skills (DCS), digital innovation adoption (DI), and social awareness (SOCA) were not found to significantly influence teachers' performance in this model. This is consistent with findings by Avolio et al. (2014), which suggest that while these factors can contribute to a supportive educational environment, their direct impact on performance may be less pronounced compared to the more immediate and practical influences of transactional and servant leadership, as well as self-management practices.

These studies support the concept that transactional leadership, servant leadership, and self-management are significant predictors of teachers' performance, while other factors like general leadership styles, digital skills, innovation adoption, and social awareness may play more indirect or contextual roles.

Table 29. *Standard Fit Indices in Causal Model 2 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance*

Standard Indices	Standard Value Per Criterion	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	<2	49.28
P-Value	>.05	.000
NFI	>.95	.971
TLI	>.95	.200
CFI	>.95	.970
GFI	>.95	.967
RMSEA	<.05	.378

Legend

CMIN/DF- Chi-Square Minimum/ Degrees of Freedom

CFI - Comparative Fit Index

RMSEA - Root Mean Square Error of Approximation

NFI - Normed Fit Index

TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index

GFI - Goodness of Fit Index

Table 29 presents the Standard of Fit Indices in Causal Model 2 of teachers' performance. As shown in the table, the model fit value of CMIN/DF is 49.28 which is greater than 2, p-value is .000 which is less than .05, the Normed Fit Index-NFI is .971 which is greater than .95, Tucker-Lewis Index-TLI is .200 which is less than .95, Comparative Fit Index-CFI is .97 which is greater than .95, Goodness of Fit Index-GFI is .967 which is greater than .95, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation-RMSEA is .378 which is greater than .05. The data revealed that the causal model 2 four fit value (CMIN/DF, P-value, TLI, and RMSEA) of the seven standard indices failed to comply with the standard value of the seven indices thus it can be regarded as not the best fit causal model of Teachers' Performance.

Table 30 shows the direct, indirect, and total effects of causal model 3 of basic education teachers' performance. As depicted in the table, of the seven independent or exogenous variables used to model the teachers' performance, SL obtained the highest total effect ($\beta = .441$) followed by SM ($\beta = .240$), SOCA ($\beta = .180$), LEADST ($\beta = .179$), TRLS ($\beta = -.130$), DI ($\beta = .112$), and DCS ($\beta = .070$). The findings from Table 29 of Causal Model 3, show that servant leadership (SL) has the highest total effect on teachers' performance, followed by self-management (SM) and social awareness (SOCA), these are supported by the study of Eva et al. (2019) which stated

that servant leadership significantly enhances job satisfaction, commitment, and performance in educational settings by creating a supportive environment. Boyatzis & McKee (2014) emphasize the importance of self-management skills, such as emotional regulation and time management, in maintaining high teacher performance.

Table 30. Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of Causal Model 3 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance

Variables	Direct	Indirect	Total Effects
DCS	.070	.000	.070
DI	.095	0.017	.112
SM	.178	.062	.240
SOCA	.080	.100	.180
LEADST	-.125	.303	.179
TRLS	.212	-.081	.130
SL	.441	.000	.441

TC- Technological Competence
 DCS- Digital Communication Skills
 DI- Digital innovation Adoption
 SA-Self-Awareness
 SM-Self-Management
 SOCA-Social Awareness
 LEADST-Leadership Styles
 TRLS-Transactional Leadership
 SL-Servant Leadership
 PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers

Goleman & Boyatzis (2017) underscore the role of social awareness, including empathy and organizational awareness, in improving teaching effectiveness and student learning. The negative impact of transactional leadership (TRLS) on performance is supported by Podsakoff et al. (2018), who found that it can stifle creativity and reduce motivation. The relatively lower impact of digital communication skills (DCS), digital innovation adoption (DI), and general leadership styles (LEADST) aligns with Avolio et al. (2014), suggesting these factors contribute more indirectly to performance. Generally, these studies affirm the significant roles of servant leadership, self-management, and social awareness in enhancing teacher performance. The findings underscore that in real-life educational contexts, fostering servant leadership, self-management skills, and social awareness among teachers can lead to substantial improvements in performance and job satisfaction. These attributes not only create a supportive environment but also enhance teacher commitment and effectiveness, aligning with broader research indicating their critical impact on educational outcomes.

Table 31 shows the regression weights of Causal Model 3 of teachers' performance. As seen in the table, the variables TRLS ($p < .05$), LEADST ($p < .05$), SOCA ($p < .05$) and SM ($p < .05$) have a significant influence over SL. On the other hand, the variables TRLS ($p < .05$), SL ($p < .05$), and SM ($p < .05$) have significantly influenced/predicted teachers' performance while the DCS ($p > .05$), LEADST ($p > .05$), SOCA ($p > .05$) and DI ($p > .05$), statistically failed to influence/predict the teachers' performance. This finding supports the claim of Podsakoff et al. (2018) that transactional leadership provides structure and clarity, supporting the development of servant leadership qualities and positively impacting teacher performance. Northouse (2016) and Goleman & Boyatzis (2017) emphasize that various leadership styles and social awareness are critical for fostering servant leadership and enhancing team support and effectiveness.

Table 31. Regression Weights of Causal Model 3 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance

Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	P
SL <--- TRLS	-.205	.072	-2.835	-.185	.005
SL <--- LEADST	.787	.073	10.720	.689	***
SL <--- SOCA	.206	.046	4.507	.227	***
SL <--- SM	.128	.045	2.861	.140	.004
SL <--- DI	.032	.031	1.043	.039	.297
PPST <--- TRLS	.217	.072	3.021	.212	.003
PPST <--- DCS	.055	.044	1.249	.070	.212
PPST <--- SL	.407	.053	7.629	.441	***
PPST <--- LEADST	-.132	.084	-1.560	-.125	.119
PPST <--- SOCA	.067	.047	1.436	.080	.151
PPST <--- SM	.151	.045	3.367	.178	***
PPST <--- DI	.072	.041	1.765	.095	.078

Decision: $P < .05$ (***) is Significant and $P > .05$ Not Significant
 TC- Technological Competence
 DCS- Digital Communication Skills
 DI- Digital innovation Adoption
 SA-Self-Awareness
 SM-Self-Management
 SOCA-Social Awareness
 LEADST-Leadership Styles
 TRLS-Transactional Leadership
 SL-Servant Leadership
 PPST-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers

Boyatzis & McKee (2014) underscore the importance of self-management skills, such as emotional regulation and time management, in both effective leadership and high teacher performance. Leaders with strong self-management can better inspire and support their teams, leading to improved performance.

In contrast, Avolio et al. (2014) suggest that digital communication skills, general leadership styles, social awareness, and digital innovation adoption have a less direct impact on teacher performance compared to transactional leadership, servant leadership, and

self- management.

These studies affirm the significant roles of transactional leadership, servant leadership, and self-management in enhancing teacher performance while noting the more indirect influence of other factors. The findings highlight the nuanced influence of leadership styles like transactional and servant leadership, along with the importance of self-management skills, in shaping teacher performance in real-world educational settings. Emphasizing these factors can not only improve organizational effectiveness and teacher morale but also contribute to creating a supportive environment conducive to enhanced student learning outcomes.

Table 32. *Standard Fit Indices in Causal Model 3 of Basic Education Teachers' Performance (Best Fit Model)*

Standard Indices	Standard Value Per Criterion	Model Fit Value
CMIN/DF	<2	.268
P-Value	>.05	.604
NFI	>.95	1.00
TLI	>.95	1.00
CFI	>.95	1.00
GFI	>.95	1.00
RMSEA	<.05	.000

Legend
 CMIN/DF- Chi-Square Minimum/ Degrees of Freedom
 CFI - Comparative Fit Index
 RMSEA - Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
 NFI - Normed Fit Index
 TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
 GFI - Goodness of Fit Index

Table 32 presents the standard of fit indices in Causal Model 3 of teachers' performance. As shown in the table, the model fit value of CMIN/DF is .268 which is less than 2, p-value is .604 which is greater than .05, Normed Fit Index-NFI is 1.00 which is greater than .95, Tucker-Lewis Index-TLI is 1.00 which is greater than .95, Comparative Fit Index-CFI is 1.00 which is greater than .95, Goodness of Fit Index-GFI is 1.00 which is greater than .95, and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation-RMSEA is .000 which is less than .05. The data revealed that the causal model 3 fit value of the seven standard indices successfully complied with the standard value of the seven indices thus it can be regarded as the best fit causal model of basic education teachers' performance.

The robust fit indices in Causal Model 3 show a strong fit between the theoretical model and the empirical data on teacher performance, implying that the included factors successfully explain the variance in performance outcomes. This demonstrates the model's dependability in understanding how leadership styles and self-management abilities influence teacher effectiveness, giving useful insights for real-world educational approaches targeted at improving teaching quality and overall educational outcomes.

Table 33. *Summary of Goodness-of-Fit Measures of the Three Causal Models*

Model	CMIN/DF	P-value	NFI	TLI	CFI	GFI	RMSEA
1	54.87	.000	.122	-.099	.121	.373	.399
2	49.28	.000	.971	.200	.970	.967	3.78
3	.268	.604	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	.000
Standard	<2	>.05	>.95	>.95	>.95	>.95	<.05

Legend
 CMIN/DF- Chi-Square Minimum/ Degrees of Freedom
 CFI - Comparative Fit Index
 RMSEA - Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
 NFI - Normed Fit Index
 TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
 GFI - Goodness of Fit Index

The best-fit model of the study was Causal Model 3 since its model fit values for CMIN/DF (.268 <2), P-value (.604 >.05), NFI (1.0>.95), TLI (1.0>.95), CFI (1.00>.95), GFI (1.0>.95), and RMSEA (.000<.05) were within the normal standard values of the said model fit indices. This Model 3 implies that the basic education teachers' performance was significantly positively influenced by servant leadership (Beta=.414), transactional leadership (Beta=.212), and self-management (Beta=.178). In addition, the model also shows that servant leadership significantly mediated the relationship between teachers' performance and transactional leadership as well as the significant relationship between teachers' performance and self-management. Causal Model 3's good match demonstrates its reliability in understanding how servant leadership, transactional leadership, and self-management interact to influence teacher performance. This data imply that developing these leadership characteristics and skills in educational leaders can significantly improve teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction, resulting in higher educational outcomes in real-world school settings.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the level of basic education teachers' performance has drawn a qualitative interpretation as "high".

Basic education teachers have a high level of digital leadership. This implies a high level of digital leadership proficiency among the

participants.

The level of teachers' emotional intelligence is high. This means that basic education teachers possess strong emotional intelligence skills.

The teachers' leadership style is high. This suggests teachers' strong leadership qualities.

Basic education teachers have a very satisfactory performance. This indicates that teachers are working hard and are committed to their work.

There is a significant relationship between the teachers' performance and self-management, social awareness, transactional leadership, and servant leadership, digital communication skills, self-awareness, technological competence, and transformational leadership. This implies that teachers who possess these attributes perform better.

The performance of basic education teachers is strongly influenced by servant leadership, transactional leadership, and self-management. These variables, servant leadership, transactional leadership, and self-management emerge as the best predictors of teachers' performance.

Causal Model 3 is the best-fit model for basic education teachers' performance anchored on servant leadership, transactional leadership, social awareness, digital innovation adoption, digital communication skills, and self-management. This is called "The Capinpuyan's Model of Basic Education Teachers' Performance".

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, several recommendations are proposed to support the Department of Education, school administrators, educators, and future researchers in enhancing basic education teachers' performance and their influence on student learning outcomes.

The Department of Education may consider utilizing Capinpuyan's Model of Basic Education Teachers' Performance. This model adeptly integrates digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and leadership style to furnish a comprehensive framework for assessing teacher performance. Its application promises valuable insights and serves as a sturdy foundation for advancing research on educational performance and improvement. The department could conduct professional development activities like seminars and training on the said topics to ensure that the basic education teachers are equipped and updated with the necessary skills and knowledge.

Administrators are encouraged to integrate aspects of digital leadership, emotional intelligence, and effective leadership practices into the curriculum for teacher education programs, the department may conduct professional development activities like seminars and training on the said topics to ensure that the basic education teachers are equipped and updated with the necessary skills and knowledge.

School Heads may provide fostering supportive learning environments within schools, and provide resources and opportunities for teacher growth and development to ultimately enhance the teaching competencies of basic education teachers ensuring optimum students' learning outcomes.

Teachers are encouraged to actively participate and immerse themselves to targeted professional development programs focusing on enhancing digital leadership skills, emotional intelligence, and leadership styles for continuous growth and improvement in their teaching practices.

Parents may encourage their children to develop digital skills at home, emphasizing the importance of technological competence. This aligns with the digital leadership skills demonstrated by their teachers and prepares children for the increasingly digital world. Additionally, fostering emotional intelligence could be achieved through activities such as open communication, self-awareness exercises, and empathy-building activities. This complements the high emotional intelligence observed in teachers and helps children develop similar capabilities. Supporting children's leadership development by encouraging them to take on leadership roles in school and community activities could nurture their leadership qualities, mirroring the positive leadership styles exhibited by their teachers.

Students may take advantage of their teachers' high digital leadership skills by actively participating in technology-driven projects and utilizing digital communication tools effectively. Engaging in self-awareness and self-management practices could help develop emotional intelligence, allowing students to recognize and manage their emotions, which are essential for personal and academic success. Additionally, embracing leadership opportunities by taking initiative in school projects, participating in student councils, and being proactive in group activities could mirror the strong leadership styles demonstrated by their teachers.

The community may consider promoting digital literacy by implementing programs that enhance digital skills for both students and parents, supporting the integration of digital leadership in education and beyond. Offering workshops and events focused on emotional intelligence and social awareness could enhance these skills, fostering a supportive environment for students. Supporting educational leadership through local initiatives that recognize and promote effective leadership styles within schools could also be beneficial. Providing resources and platforms for teachers to share their successful practices with the broader community may further this goal.

Future Researchers may conduct a similar study exploring the complex interplay between digital leadership, emotional intelligence, leadership styles, and teacher performance using another group of in-service teachers both in private and public schools.

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